

Polarographic Study of Complexes of Lead(II), Copper(II), Cadmium(II) and Zinc(II) with Cyclohexylthioglycolate and Hexylthioglycolate

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The complexation of Pb^{II}, Cu^{II}, Cd^{II} and Zn^{II} by cyclohexylthioglycolate and hexylthioglycolate has been studied polarographically. The reduction of Pb^{II} has been found to be reversible and diffusion-controlled involving a two-electron transfer process, while the reduction of Cu^{II}, Cd^{II} and Zn^{II} has been found to be irreversible and diffusion-controlled in both the cases. The stability constants of Pb^{II} has been calculated by DeFord and Hume's method, while Crow's mean diffusion coefficient method has been used in case of the other metal complexes which are reduced irreversibly.

A survey of literature reveals that the complexation of Pb^{II}, Cu^{II}, Cd^{II} and Zn^{II} in aqueous and aquo-organic media has been studied with some thio-organic reagents such as thiodipropionic acid¹, methoxyethylthioglycolate³, thioglycolic acid⁴, morpholine-*N*-dithiocarbamate⁵, sulphosalicylic acid⁶, ethylthioglycolate⁷, thiolactic acid⁸, thiomalic acid⁹, diethyldithiocarbamate¹⁰, *n*-butylthioglycolate¹¹ and β -mercaptopropionic acid¹².

The present communication reports the polarographic behaviour of Pb^{II}, Cd^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} with cyclohexylthioglycolate (CyHTG) and hexylthioglycolate (HTG) in ethanol-water mixture with KNO₃ or KCl as the supporting electrolyte.

Method of calculation : The change in diffusion current ($\Delta \bar{i}_d$) of a metal ion due to the presence of increasing concentration of a ligand is proportional to the average ligand number¹³,

$$\bar{n} \simeq k \Delta \bar{i}_d \quad (1)$$

where k is a characteristic constant. Thus the square-root of the diffusion coefficient of an individual complex MLo...ML_{*n*} in a metal-ligand system varies linearly with the coordination number. A plot of $\Delta \bar{i}_d$ vs log [L] will have the same sigmoidal shape as the plot of \bar{n} vs log [L], and the former is designated as the pseudo-formation curve¹⁴ which may be used to obtain a series of provisional values for the formation constants. The two related types of data are linked via the F_0 [L] functions of Leden¹⁵,

$$\frac{d \log F_0 [L]}{d \log [L]} = \bar{n} \simeq k \Delta \bar{i}_d \quad (2)$$

$$\text{i.e. } \frac{d \log F_0 [L]}{k d \log [L]} = \frac{d \log F_0' [L]}{d \log [L]} = \Delta \bar{i}_d \quad (3)$$

$$\log F_0 [L] = \int_0^{[L]} \Delta \bar{i}_d d \log [L] \quad (4)$$

It is now possible to perform a series of Leden type graphical analysis for various selected integral or intermediate values of k to find which gives a sensible family of derived curves. In order to find log F_0 data from log F_0' , it is required to calculate the values of k in equations (2) and (3). A simple and useful approach is to plot the values of function log F_0 [L] vs $-\log [L]$. The limiting slope of log [L] $\rightarrow 0$ is \bar{n}_{\max}/k .

Results and Discussion

Single well-defined waves were obtained with all the metal ions. The plots of i_d vs \sqrt{h} (where h is effective height of mercury column) and i_d vs C (where C is metal ion concentration) were linear and passed through the origin. The log plots were linear with a slope of 32 ± 2 mV in the case of Pb^{II} thus showing that the reduction process is diffusion-controlled and reversible two-electron step. The diffusion-current decreased and $E_{1/2}$ shifted to more negative values together with the increase of reagent concentration. Thus Pb^{II} has been found to form complexes with cyclohexylthioglycolate and hexylthioglycolate. The plots of $E_{1/2}$ vs $-\log [L]$ (where L is concentration of cyclohexylthioglycolate or hexylthioglycolate) were smooth curves showing the formation of more than one complex simultaneously. The composition and formation constants of the complexes formed were calculated by the Deford and Hume's method¹⁷ and results are given in Table 1. Preliminary experiments pertaining to the nature of the cathodic waves of Cd^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} showed that these metal ions are reduced irreversibly by CyHTG and HTG.

The values k were calculated for Cd^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} (Tables 2 and 3). Multiplying k by log F_0' gives the log F_0 [L] values. The intercepts of F_j [L] vs [L] plots on F_j [L] axis give the values of the

TABLE 1—STABILITY CONSTANTS AND THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS OF LEAD WITH CYCLOHEXYLTHIOGLYCOLATE AND HEXYLTHIOGLYCOLATE

Composition of complex	log β	Thermodynamic parameters					
		ΔG kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔH* kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔS JK mol ⁻¹	ΔG kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔH** kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔS JK mol ⁻¹
Lead-cyclonexylthioglycolate system							
1:1	2.4	-13.96	32	152	-14.42	19.0	109
1:2	2.8	-16.26	49	215	-16.79	45.0	197
Lead-hexylthioglycolate system							
1:1	2.1	-12.62	20	108	-13.04	36	157
1:2	3.4	-19.91	27	155	-20.56	24	143

*At 30°. **At 40°.

TABLE 2—COMPLEXATION DATA WITH CYCLOHEXYLTHIOGLYCOLATE

[L] mmol dm ⁻³ vs SCE	-E _{1/2} V	i _d (μA)	log F ₀	10 ⁻² F ₀	10 ⁻³ F ₁	10 ⁻⁹ F ₂
Cu ^{II} =1 mmol dm ⁻³ , log F ₀ is obtained by multiplying log F' ₀ with k=2.993						
0.00	0.560	5.56	—	—	—	—
0.01	0.580	5.52	0.879 6	—	—	—
0.05	0.590	5.49	1.319 6	0.208	—	—
0.10	0.610	5.47	2.199 2	1.582	0.582 0	—
0.20	0.620	5.45	2.639 0	4.355	1.677 5	5.477
0.50	0.630	5.42	3.079 0	11.995	2.191 0	3.218
1.00	0.640	5.41	3.518 8	33.021	3.202 0	2.620
3.00	0.660	5.40	4.398 8	250.495	8.316 5	2.578
5.00	0.670	5.32	4.838 6	686.435	13.708 0	2.625
log K ₁ =5.76, log K ₂ =9.42						
[L] mmol dm ⁻³	-E _{1/2} (V)	i _d (μA)	log F ₀	10 ⁻³ F ₀	10 ⁻⁵ F ₁	10 ⁻⁹ F ₂
Cd ^{II} =1 mmol dm ⁻³ , log F ₀ is obtained by multiplying log F' ₀ with k=2.184						
0.00	0.800	4.82	—	—	—	—
0.01	0.832	4.78	1.025 0	0.105 9	—	—
0.05	0.842	4.75	1.346 0	0.222 0	4.240	—
0.10	0.860	4.73	1.922 8	0.837 3	8.273	—
0.50	0.880	4.69	2.563 5	3.660 0	7.300	6.129
1.00	0.900	4.67	2.883 8	7.653 0	7.683	3.403
3.00	0.915	4.66	3.684 0	48.383 8	16.124	3.961
5.00	0.925	4.58	4.005 0	101.175 0	20.233	3.198
log K ₁ =5.62, log K ₂ =8.54						
[L] mmol dm ⁻³	-E _{1/2} (V)	i _d (μA)	log F ₀	10 ⁻³ F ₀	10 ⁻⁵ F ₁	10 ⁻⁹ F ₂
Zn ^{II} =1 mmol dm ⁻³ , log F ₀ is obtained by multiplying log F' ₀ with k=2.758						
0.00	0.950	8.632	—	—	—	—
0.01	0.980	8.542	1.217	0.016 5	—	—
0.05	0.990	8.522	1.622	0.041 8	8.177	—
0.10	1.010	8.502	2.433	0.271 0	27.010	18.830
0.50	1.040	8.482	3.647	4.434 0	88.670	16.099
1.00	1.060	8.462	4.458	28.708 0	287.070	27.880
2.00	1.070	8.452	4.855	71.614 0	358.060	17.490
5.00	1.090	8.442	5.655	451.856 0	903.710	17.910
log K ₁ =5.91, log K ₂ =10.24						

formation constants. The overall stability constants (log β) for the series of complexes have also been calculated. The values of overall changes

TABLE 3—COMPLEXATION DATA WITH HEXYLTHIOGLYCOLATE

[L] mmol dm ⁻³ vs SCE	-E _{1/2} (V)	i _d (μA)	log F ₀	10 ⁻² F ₀	10 ⁻⁶ F ₁	10 ⁻¹⁰ F ₂
Cu ^{II} =1 mmol dm ⁻³ , log F ₀ is obtained by multiplying log F' ₀ with k=3.018						
0.00	0.560	5.56	—	—	—	—
0.01	0.578	5.48	0.800	0.063	0.531	—
0.05	0.598	5.46	1.686	0.485	0.950	0.838 2
0.10	0.615	5.44	2.440	2.754	2.744	2.212 5
0.50	0.637	5.42	3.416	26.061	5.210	0.935 7
1.00	0.657	5.41	4.300	199.526	19.951	19.419 0
3.00	0.667	5.40	4.744	554.625	18.487	0.598 5
5.00	0.677	5.36	5.188	1541.700	30.833	0.606 0
log K ₁ =6.72, log K ₂ =9.77						
[L] mmol dm ⁻³	-E _{1/2} (V)	i _d (μA)	log F ₀	10 ⁻² F ₀	10 ⁻⁴ F ₁	10 ⁻⁸ F ₂
Cd ^{II} =1 mmol dm ⁻³ , log F ₀ is obtained by multiplying log F' ₀ with k=2.000						
0.00	0.800	4.82	—	—	—	—
0.01	0.815	4.73	0.442	0.276	17.60	—
0.05	0.835	4.70	1.029	0.107	19.41	3.600
0.10	0.858	4.68	1.706	0.508	49.81	3.210
0.50	0.875	4.66	2.204	1.599	31.79	2.838
1.00	0.895	4.65	2.792	6.166	61.56	4.396
3.00	0.915	4.62	3.380	23.980	79.92	2.077
5.00	0.930	4.56	3.820	66.069	132.12	2.290
log K ₁ =4.24, log K ₂ =8.34						
[L] mmol dm ⁻³	-E _{1/2} (V)	i _d (μA)	log F ₀	10 ⁻² F ₀	10 ⁻⁸ F ₁	10 ⁻¹⁰ F ₂
Zn ^{II} =1 mmol dm ⁻³ , log F ₀ is obtained by multiplying log F' ₀ with k=2.993						
0.00	0.950	8.632	—	—	—	—
0.01	0.972	8.528	0.969	0.093	0.831	—
0.05	0.998	8.508	2.112	1.294	2.568	3.47
0.10	1.014	8.482	2.816	6.546	6.536	5.70
0.50	1.034	8.462	3.695	49.545	9.907	1.81
1.00	1.054	8.442	4.573	374.110	37.410	3.65
2.00	1.068	8.430	5.189	1545.250	77.260	3.82
5.00	1.078	8.418	5.629	4255.980	85.120	1.68
log K ₁ =5.92, log K ₂ =10.57						

in free energy (ΔG), enthalpy (ΔH) and the entropy (ΔS) on the formation of complexes have been determined and results are given in Tables 2 and 3. The free energy and enthalpy of formation have large negative values and entropy change have high positive values in each case, indicating spontaneity of complex formation. The results are given in Table 4.

Experimental

The polarograms were obtained with a manual Toshniwal polarograph (ClO₂ type). The d.m.e. had the following characteristics: m=3.5 mg s⁻¹ and t=2.6 s in an open-circuit.

Reagent grade chemicals were used. Stock solutions (0.01M) of Pb^{II}, Cd^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} were prepared using lead nitrate, cadmium acetate, copper chloride and zinc nitrate respectively.

TABLE 4—OVERALL STABILITY CONSTANTS AND THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS OF BIVALENT METAL COMPLEXES WITH CYCLOHEXYL THIOGLYCOLATE (CyHTG) AND HEXYL THIOGLYCOLATE (HTG)

T K	log β	ΔG kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔH kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔS JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
Cu-CyHTG				
293	15.18	-85.18	-33	-172
303	14.86	-86.23		
313	14.35	-86.80		
Cd-CyHTG				
293	14.08	-79.83	-31	162
303	13.77	-80.00		
313	13.42	-80.52		
Zn-CyHTG				
293	16.16	-90.76	-29	207
303	15.80	-91.77		
313	15.55	-93.30		
Cu-HTG				
293	16.50	-92.69	-38	183
303	16.10	-93.53		
313	15.60	-93.61		
Cd-HTG				
293	12.59	-71.26	-23	159
303	12.31	-71.49		
313	12.11	-72.05		
Zn-HTG				
293	16.49	-92.62	-35	193
303	16.09	-93.45		
313	15.69	94.14		

Cyclohexylthioglycolate and hexylthioglycolate were prepared by the reported method¹⁶ and their stock solutions (0.1%) were made in ethanol. Proper amount (0.1%) Triton X-100 solution was used as the maxima suppressor wherever needed. Ionic strength was maintained at $\mu=0.5$ by adding KNO₃ or KCl. pH was measured using a digital pH

meter and adjusted in the range of 3.0–10.5 for Pb, 4.2–8.5 for Cd, 3.5–5.5 for Cu and 5.5–8.0 for Zn. The polarograms were recorded in 40–60% ethanol medium. The necessary correction for the ir drop and the residual current was applied in determining the half-wave potential and diffusion-current data respectively.

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